

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. EDNA M. HERRERA

Associate Professor III

University of Rizal System

ednaherrera138@gmail.com

“HOW LEARNING DRAFTING HELPS STUDENTS?”

Drafting plays a vital role in developing the technical skills and intellectual abilities of learners. Drafting is often referred to as the universal language of industry and design. It helps in visualizing the ideas of a person. It can develop the creativity of a person and if made possible there will be no limit to the imagination of the mind.

One significant benefit of learning Drafting is the development of accuracy and attention to detail. This trains the students to be organized and methodical in their work which are valuable traits not just at work but also on a daily basis. Another benefit is its application in various industries. Drafting can be used from designing floor plans to creating mechanical parts, it provides learners with skills that are relevant in this technology-driven world. It opens opportunities for careers in design, construction, manufacturing, and education especially to BTVTED students who will be future educators. Drafting also nurtures the creativity and innovation of the learners, from this knowledge and skills they will be able to develop a mindset that values both aesthetics and functionality, to aim to develop something that is both pleasing to the eyes and highly functioning. Tasks in drafting can be a time-consuming task making the learners develop strategies to plan, organize, and execute their work efficiently, which can be applied not only in their professional life but also in their personal life.

Drafting can help the learners not just in sharpening their critical thinking but also encouraging creativity. For future professionals, mastering drafting is an investment it provides real-world applications not just in career readiness but also in personal growth.

